

Flood Inundation from Urban Impervious Surfaces: *Flood inundation risk reduction using Smart Growth development*

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Abstract To minimize urban flood inundation risk from impervious surfaces, the use of the Smart Growth development methodology is recommended in lieu of recent sprawl-type development methods in widespread use. Based on the technical and scientific review of the impervious surface literature (Shuster, et al., 2005; SCS, 1986; Brody, et al., 2007; Schuler, et al., 2009; Boyd, et al., 1993; Arnold and Gibbons, 1996) for the preparation of Sections 1, 2, and 3, it is apparent that the concept of impervious surface in urban planning and flood hydrology are poorly understood, imprecisely measured, and appear haphazardly throughout the literature lacking full, clear, and consistent definition, i.e., TIA versus EIA, effective or disconnected? This state has perpetuated non-uniform application of impervious surface concepts and fostered simplistic interpretations of observations and hydrographic data for mitigating urban flood inundation. Yet, viewing the literature (as a whole) observations can be made of key points where impervious surface concepts interface with urban hydrology. These key nexus points, which should be viewed as aspects of development to be avoided or minimized, may be useful in achieving deeper understanding of impervious surface. The outcomes of a mathematical modeling study (Bierwagen et al., 2010), are reviewed and positive findings attributed to Smart Growth development methods are highlighted. The spatial relationships between developed areas, natural hydrologic features, and stormwater conveyance systems are complex and interrelated; relationships which are not adequately described simple site scoring or rudimentary metrics on percent impervious surface.

1. Introduction

Widespread methods of urban development impede the natural cycle of infiltration of precipitation. Impeding natural infiltration modifies watershed hydrology, increasing the volume and timing of runoff from developed surfaces and, depending on the amount of precipitation and extent of development, inundating neighborhoods, businesses, and transportation networks, and harming urban stream ecosystems with high volume discharge - eroding sediment in streams, damaging habitat, and degrading water quality.

A clarification on terminology usage in this paper. Traditionally the hydrologic term **flood** is *any* peak flow value in a stream-flow hydrograph. In common colloquial usage, flood is apparently used to mean inundation. To avoid confusion, in this paper I use **flood inundation** to refer to the presence of unwanted water in the urban environment.

In this paper I examine and clarify the concept of an *impervious surface*; explain the different classifications and *conventions* of impervious surface appearing throughout the literature; describe examples to illustrate how an *impervious surface* contributes to stormwater runoff volume, increasing urban flood inundation

risk. Finally, I analyze and describe how the use of Smart Growth development strategies are effective in reducing flood inundation risk.

2. Review of Impervious Surface Concept

An impervious surface is a human-made material or structure used in urban development that slows the rate of precipitation infiltration. An impervious surface can also be created (either intentionally or, unintentionally) by altering the compaction of natural materials, slowing the rate of precipitation infiltration. For example, coincident compaction of near-surface sediments by construction vehicle traffic or the intentional compaction (engineering design required) of backfill under a load bearing surface. In short, an impervious surface causes precipitation to flow overland (referred to as runoff) instead of infiltrating naturally into the ground (Shuster, et al., 2005; SCS, 1986; Brody, et al., 2007; Schuler, et al., 2009; Boyd, et al., 1993; Arnold and Gibbons, 1996)

- This definition of impervious surface does not imply that a surface and/or material must be completely impervious to water penetration, but rather means only that a material sufficiently impedes the flow of water to cause ponding which increases runoff volume. Examples of impervious surfaces commonly encountered in urban development and materials are listed in Table 1.
- Not all impervious surfaces present the same flood inundation risk; this risk varies based on the local position and design (neighborhood scale) and geographic location (watershed scale) of the impervious surface.
- The most general and simplistic classification of impervious surface as described in the scientific literature is known as total impervious surface (TIA). TIA is usually presented as a percent of total land area. For example, as shown in Table 2, if a land lot is measured to be 1,000 feet squared (ft²), and the building, drive, and parking lot together occupy 800 ft² of the land lot, then TIA is equal to 80 percent. TIA may best represent an estimated measure of total developed area and not of flood inundation risk from runoff; a TIA measure fails to adequately account for areas of impervious materials that area isolated from drainage networks and therefore may not directly contribute to increasing surface runoff volume. Because some areas of impervious surface areas are isolated and disconnected (for example, a roof draining only onto a natural landscape area for infiltration, not runoff), the concept of effectiveness was introduced.
- An effective impervious surface (EIA) is located to be hydraulically connected to a drainage network, and thus can contribute to the total area runoff volume. Conversely, an ineffective impervious surface is located to be hydraulically disconnected from a drainage network and may not contribute to the total area runoff volume. For example, precipitation surface runoff flowing from a roof may be termed connected if the surface runoff flows into the stormwater collection network, e.g., stormwater inlet or urban drainage stream. However, if the roof surface runoff enters a roof gutter and flows instead onto the landscaping (for subsequent forced infiltration into the ground), the runoff should be termed ineffective and disconnected.
- Some landscaped areas can produce significant volumes of runoff from precipitation. During land development, some areas are compacted from repeated, heavy construction vehicle traffic; only later is the compacted land covered with top soil and planted with landscaping or sod placed – giving the illusion of undisturbed land. However, these compacted areas will produce effective runoff contributing the total runoff volume and increasing flood inundation risk. Photographs of

the property taken during development activities can be helpful to the analyst to identify compacted areas; perhaps more importantly are the observations of the construction inspector who should carefully document areas of compaction.

Stormwater conveyance sewers confound the clear distinction and relative importance to flood inundation risk from connected impervious surface areas versus disconnected impervious surface areas. This is because a stormwater conveyance sewer collects and concentrates surface water runoff across a (wide) area of an urban development, allowing surface runoff to bypass potential infiltration on the landscape.

Thus, for a flood inundation risk analysis to be robust and meaningful, the relative spatial relationship of each element (TIA, EIA, effective areas, ineffective/disconnected areas, and the extent and locations of stormwater conveyance sewers) all must be known. The use of a geographic information system will facilitate this type of analysis. Importantly, knowledge of the difference between the various classifications of impervious surface i.e., TIA, EIA, connected areas versus disconnected areas, is crucial when reviewing and comparing runoff studies since *how* an impervious surface was classified in an analysis can produce very different analysis outcomes (for either empirical and/or modeling simulation studies) – which ultimately guides management decisions for flood inundation risk mitigation.

3. What are the risks from impervious surfaces?

The risks to the urban environment from impervious surfaces (i.e., surfacewater runoff, flood inundation), can impact both the built human environment and the natural environment. Damage from excessive volumes of surfacewater runoff effects urban stream networks. This damage is known in the literature as the Urban Stream Syndrome (Walsh, et al., 2005) and has been extensively studied and well documented. Physical changes to a stream's structure (from excessive sedimentation and/or erosion from altered flow volumes) and physiochemical changes to water quality (e.g., water temperature, pH) disrupt habitats and alter ecosystems. Too much impervious surface can produce excessive volumes of stormwater runoff, overwhelming stormwater management system and producing inundation flooding.

This cause and effect has been documented in numerous studies. One interesting example was published by hydrologists with the US Geological Survey (Anderson 1974) (USGS) in collaboration with Johns Hopkins University (John Geyer, PhD) and the University of Delaware (Donald Dean, PhD), where impervious surfaces from urbanization were determined as the cause of urban inundation flooding in northern Virginia and Washington, D.C. The investigators concluded,

“The relations indicate that urban and suburban development significantly changes flood magnitudes. On small, steep basins, drainage improvements alone may triple the average flood magnitude, and complete development of stream channels with a 100-percent impervious cover may increase average flood by a factor of nearly eight.”

Brody et al. (2007) examined 383 individual inundation floods to investigate linkages between urban development and inundation flooding. The investigators concluded that the **location** and **intensity** of urban development effects community risk to inundation flooding. As an example:

- the natural hydrologic cycle is regulated in-part by the *geographic location* of important natural features, e.g., wetlands, springs, aquifer recharge and discharge areas, stream networks, forested watersheds, and so on. When the location of urban development interferes with the functioning of the natural hydrologic cycle (for example, when a commercial building and parking lot are

constructed over an aquifer recharge area, reducing natural recharge and storage of precipitation) the hydrologic system is forced out of its natural state of balance and the risks of inundation flooding (from increased stormwater runoff volume, increase.

4. Urban sprawl and the benefits of adopting smart growth development methods

Based on the technical and scientific review of the impervious surface literature for the preparation of Sections 1, 2, and 3, it is apparent that the concept of impervious surface in urban planning and flood hydrology are poorly understood, imprecisely measured, and appear haphazardly throughout the literature lacking full, clear, and consistent definition, i.e., TIA versus EIA, effective or disconnected? This state has perpetuated non-uniform application of impervious surface concepts and fostered simplistic interpretations of observations and hydrographic data for mitigating urban flood inundation.

Yet, viewing the literature (as a whole), observations can be made of key points where impervious surface concepts interface with urban hydrology. These key nexus points, which should be viewed as aspects of development to be avoided or minimized, may be useful in achieving deeper understanding of impervious surface.

Key Observations/Points are:

- **Extent** of land development, i.e., the total land area (especially natural, undeveloped land) converted to urban use, includes stormwater sewer conveyance systems
- **Parcel location** and **spatial relationships** relative to the geographic location of important natural features regulating the terrestrial portion of the hydrologic cycle and natural conveyance of stormwater, e.g., aquifer recharge and discharge areas,
- **Intensity / density** of land development

Not one key observation is more important than another point; ultimately, the impact on stormwater management depends on the spatial relationship (local and/or regional context) between one key observation and the other observations. The spatial relationships between developed areas, natural hydrologic features, and stormwater conveyance systems are complex and interrelated; relationships which are not adequately described simple site scoring or rudimentary metrics on percent impervious surface. Lastly, the intensity of development is a measure of how much natural land area is left undisturbed by development. The land areas may be contiguous or fragmented; the importance depends on the natural hydrologic features disturbed and local and/or regional context.

The extent of land development refers to how much land is converted from natural to urban use. It is synonymous with urban sprawl, and results in greater and greater amounts of natural areas and important hydrologic features (such as wetlands, for example) being destroyed and displaced.

The nexus points operate independently or with other points in various states of minimization along a continuum – a highly complex relationship. While it may be possible to perform advanced mathematical modeling on such a complex system to investigate such a system, the input data requirements and modeling time required to build and document such a simulation - for every area under development - would be cost prohibitive. There is, fortunately, an alternative development methodology called Smart Growth, that seeks to minimize the negative aspects of land development contributing to the spread of impervious surface and urban flood inundation.

There are many positive elements of Smart Growth development that can contribute positively to our modern society. However, I will discuss only those aspects which are directly related to minimizing impervious surface and urban flood inundation. The Smart Growth paradigm seeks to minimize sprawl-type development by fostering compact, dense development near where people work and live, and thus avoiding the conversion of natural land (and hydrologic features) for urban uses. Less sprawl and reduced or eliminated conversion of natural land means less interference with important elements of the terrestrial portion of the hydrologic cycle. The approach to neighborhood development and stormwater management under Smart Growth seeks to preserve existing landforms and natural drainage and conveyance features, thus minimizing area impacts, and the spatial relationships between developed areas and natural features of hydrologic importance.

4.1 Case Study – Modeling landuse data complexity to develop national housing and impervious surface scenarios.

Bierwagen et al., 2010 published in the proceedings of the (US) National Academy of Science a data analysis and multi-scenario modeling investigation of population and housing density. While the focus of the investigation was much more broad in scope than only land development and impervious surface and included critical examination and integration of emission scenarios, country-scale population shifts to examine how appropriate landuse planning can create positive effects to reduce climate change impacts, the investigation did produce some results that are directly relevant to this paper.

Key findings are summarized below:

- “In general, there are significant difference between the amount of impervious surface cover that can result from different growth scenarios”
- “The compact scenarios resulted in less impervious surface cover over time, particularly in conjunction with low domestic migration, which reduces new housing development and favors higher-density housing allocation”
- “The difference among scenarios illustrate the potential impacts of policies that limit the amount of impervious surface cover, such as Smart Growth planning principles”
- “...converting commercial or industrial landuse (*read: not converting natural land for urban use*) can also alter this relationship and improve water quality and aquatic ecosystem conditions in watersheds”
- “Compact development patterns can reduce habitat loss and the number of impaired watersheds”

Importantly, the investigators made an early assumption that shaped the outcome of the analysis results. The investigators assumed no change in the dominant paradigm in housing and community development over the duration of the simulation to 2100, i.e., that sprawl-type developments will persist to be the dominant mode of development.

The outcomes of the modeling investigation would have been very different if the authors would have assumed the wide spread adoption of the Smart Growth development method. While this analysis produced some interesting results relevant to this paper, the authors failed to recognize and acknowledge the importance of spatial relationships with between the urban and natural hydrologic features, how the relationships interact to increase the risks of urban flood inundation. The authors used extensive datasets and computer modeling to simulate the occurrence of impervious surfaces, unfortunately there was not a

focus on what conditions create urban flood inundation risks or under what conditions synergistic effects are created to increase the risk of urban flood inundation.

5. Conclusion

The scientific and planning literature is filled with reports of investigation of urban development, impervious surfaces, and associated urban flood inundation risks. Many of these reports suggest use of simplistic ranking systems and rudimentary measures of impervious surface as a means of managing flood inundation risk to developed area. These simplistic relations are inadequate to simulate the behavior of a complex system with multiple variables each element influences the other along a continuum. A more effective approach to minimizing the creation of dangerous conditions of urban flood inundation is the use of an alternative land development paradigm, Smart Growth development methodology. Smart Growth development methodology can minimize or eliminate many negative aspects of development (associated with sprawl-type development) including aspects directly responsible for the cause of urban flood inundation.

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Tables

Table 1. Examples of impervious surfaces in urban development

Table 2. TIA Calculation

Table 1.
Examples of impervious surfaces in urban development

Surfaces/Structures	Materials
Roof	Asphalt
Roadway	Tin
Driveway	Concrete
Parking Lot	Clay, Silt, fine Sand (compacted)
Culvert	

Table 2. TIA calculation

General Impervious Area	Mathematical Operation	Total Land Lot Area	TIA Solution
800 ft ²	÷	1000 ft ²	0.8

To convert the TIA solution to a percentage following this example: $0.8 \times 100 = 80\%$